

The intersections of FAIRplus outputs and the ELIXIR Platforms

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The FAIRplus project, funded by the Innovative Medicine Initiative ([IMI](#) - now the Innovative Health Initiative, IHI), brought together partners from academia and pharma in order to develop tools and guidelines for the FAIRification of life science data.

A number of technical and scientific outputs of interest to the ELIXIR Platforms, and especially to the Interoperability Platform, have been generated by this project. This report summarises the key FAIRplus outputs of interest to the ELIXIR Platforms.

Interoperability Platform

Due to the Interoperability Platform's role in promoting FAIR services across the life sciences, the set of FAIRification tools that have been developed in FAIRplus are of great importance to this Platform.

Perhaps the most well-known resource in the context of the Interoperability Platform is [The FAIR Cookbook](#), which contains recipes for FAIRification ([Rocca-Serra et al., 2022](#)). This resource, along with other well-known resources such as the [Data Stewardship Wizard](#) and [RDMkit](#), will form the basis of the Interoperability Platform's research data management portfolio which is to be carried forward into the next ELIXIR Programme from 2024 - 2028. Notably the FAIR Cookbook has been adopted into the national service delivery plans of ELIXIR-LU and ELIXIR-UK, with Switzerland and Spain currently adding it into theirs.

Additionally, the [FAIR Wizard](#) facilitates the use of the recipes in the FAIR Cookbook by providing guidance on the most suitable recipes.

Data Platform

As a part of the FAIRplus project, a number of IMI datasets were selected to undergo FAIRification, which creates an interesting case study for how to prioritise datasets for FAIRification, and resulted in a number of useful outputs. These include an outline of the considerations and process of dataset FAIRification ([Alharbi et al., 2022](#)), the [FAIR-Decide](#) framework which assists with cost-benefit analysis of retrospective FAIRification in pharmaceutical R&D, a recipe for "[Prioritisation of projects for FAIRification](#)" (recipe FCB055), the [FAIR Dataset Maturity \(DSM\) Model](#) which provides a means for measuring how FAIR a dataset is, and a [FAIRification Framework](#) (recipe FCB079) which provides a starting point for data or project owners who wish to begin the FAIRification process on their own

data. Additionally, the [Translational Data Catalogue \(Welter et al., 2022\)](#) provides a single discovery point for data from EU-funded projects.

Training Platform

One of the goals of FAIRplus was to deliver training through the [FAIRplus Fellowship programme](#), which was successfully completed by a first contingent of students. There are plans to link in a network of research data management experts to continue to develop the materials, which are currently available on the Fraunhofer website, and are to be listed on [TeSS](#) to improve their findability.

Beyond Platforms

Some of the outputs of FAIRplus are not specific to any Platform, but were useful and impactful, and may be worth considering in future work. These are listed below.

Ways of Working

The multi-disciplinary cross-workstream [squads](#) proved to be a highly effective mode of working and may be a useful precedent to bear in mind for future projects.

Legal

Due to the sensitive nature of some of the data involved in this project, it is worth highlighting the [Data Protection Impact Assessment](#) (FCB074). Legal considerations are also covered in the [Reflections of the Ethical Values of FAIR](#) (FCB072).

Industry Partners

As a part of FAIRplus sustainability planning, it was highlighted by the consortium that some of the greatest benefits of the project have also been the intangible benefits, such as the connections that were forged between industry and academia partners. In light of this, a FAIR workshop is scheduled to be hosted in 2023 as part of the [EMBL-EBI Industry Programme](#).

Network of Experts

Finally, the network of FAIR experts that grew out of FAIRplus will find a useful touchpoint with the newly approved ELIXIR Community in the area of research data management.

Conclusion

The FAIRplus project brought together numerous partners from academia and industry, united by the common goal of FAIRification in the life sciences. A number of valuable resources have been developed over the course of the project, and the ELIXIR Platforms can play an important role in the long-term sustainability of these resources at the same time as improving the levels of FAIR in the life sciences.